

The Impact of Shipping Costs and Advertising on Shopee Buying Interest from Shopee in Students of Economic Education Study Universitas HKBP Nommensen Pematangsiantar Year 2019

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine the effect of free shipping and advertising on buying interest from Shopee among students of the 2019 Stambuk economics education study program at HKBP Nommensen Pematangsiantar University. The variables in this research are free shipping and advertising as the independent variable and purchase interest as the dependent variable. This type of research is quantitative research with a survey data analysis approach, with the research population being all students from group A and B of the 2019 Stambuk Economics Education Study Program at HKBP Nommensen Pematang Siantar University and the sample for this research is group B students, totaling 60 students. Data collection techniques use instruments: (1) free postage questionnaire, (2) advertising, and (3) purchase interest. The results of this research show that: (1) there is a positive and significant influence of free shipping on purchase interest, this result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value > t table ($3.223 > 1.6715$) (sig.) < 0.05 as much as 0 Free Shipping and Advertising on buying interest from shopee 025, then it is significant. (2) there is a positive and significant influence of advertising on buying interest, this result can be seen in the t test where the t-count value > t-table ($2.407 > 1.6715$) with (sig.) < 0.05, namely 0.05, then significant. (3) Free shipping and advertising together influence purchasing interest, this result can be seen in the F test where the F-calculated value is higher than the F-table ($5.738 > 3.15$) and the significance is lower than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). The R Square coefficient of determination test is known to be 0.138, which means that 13.8% of the free shipping and advertising variables influence the buying interest of students in the 2019 Stambuk Economics Education Study Program, HKBP Nommensen University, Pematang Siantar and the remaining 86.2% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

INTRODUCTION

Current technological developments in the era of globalization are able to bring changes to human life . One of the changes that is very rapid and very inherent in meeting needs is technological progress, especially in the internet sector. The Internet is a network that can connect many computers to send news, obtain information and transfer data. The reason is that most students are often hesitant to shop online because of the shipping costs they have to pay so that the goods purchased online can arrive at their homes.

With the free shipping promo by providing free shipping to buyers so that students don't mind making purchases so that consumers will be interested in buying from Shopee. In this research, there are many online shops in e-commerce in the online business program , one of which is Shopee. Shopee is a start-up company from Singapore which entered Indonesia in December 2015. Therefore, when consumers make purchases offline, students must meet with the seller of the product, the seller and the buyer and must meet face to face until an agreement is reached between the seller and the buyer.

Shopee has a special attraction in the minds of students. Shopee is famous for its free shipping program throughout Indonesia. The free shipping program is a form of promotion carried out by the company by covering the costs of sending products to the buyer's address, but with certain conditions. Additional services with a free shipping policy have provided new opportunities to meet customer needs and increase company profits.

Advertisements are messages delivered with the aim of introducing a product to an audience on a particular media platform. The role of advertising in influencing consumers to make consumers consume a brand is believed to be very important. This makes effective advertising activities seen as capable of influencing people's consumption tendencies. The ultimate goal is of course to persuade people to buy the products offered.

The interest that arises in making a purchase gives rise to motivation which continues to be recorded in his mind and becomes a very strong activity which in the end when a consumer has to fulfill his needs he will actualize what is in his mind. The reason is that most consumers often hesitate to shop online because of the shipping costs they have to pay so that the goods purchased online can reach their homes.

Then consumers will see the promotion given by Shopee, namely a free shipping promo where consumers will be attracted by the free shipping by eliminating shipping costs and then consumers will make purchases. In this research, the researchers used free shipping and advertising as independent variables and purchase interest as the dependent variable. Based on the problems above, researchers are interested in researching with the title: " The Impact of Shipping Costs and Advertising on Shopee Buying Interest from Shopee in Students of Economic Education Study Universitas HKBP Nommensen Pematangsiantar Year 2019"

THEORETICAL REVIEW

1. Free Shipping

According to Amalia & Wibowo (2019), free shipping promotions are another form of sales promotion that uses various incentives to stimulate product purchases as soon as possible and increase the quantity of products purchased by consumers . Meanwhile, according to Himayati (2008: 34) shipping costs are the costs of sending goods or services collected by the seller from the customer during the buying and

selling process with shipping costs charged to the customer. It can be concluded that free shipping is the cost of sending goods or services free of charge which is usually collected by the seller from the customer during the buying and selling process. This free shipping can be interpreted as shipping costs that are waived from the buyer without being charged a shipping fee. This aims to attract consumers to buy products on Shopee with free shipping.

2. Advertisement

According to Fatihudin and Firmansyah (2019: 164) Advertising is a communication model that can reach the public at large. Advertising can be used to build a long-term image and also speed up quick sales. Apart from that, advertisements are also standard and can be shown repeatedly and can get a dramatization effect from the advertisements that are shown. Furthermore, according to Jaiz (2014: 4), advertising is any form of message about a product conveyed through the media, shown to some or all of society. From the definition of advertising according to experts who have been explained by researchers, the definition of advertising is a work in the form of audio-visual work, a series of words and sound as a form of content that produces a message, an incitement or invitation to the public regarding the product or service offered by the marketer. which makes anyone see or hear about it through the media on TV, posters, magazines, radio and social media and will be tempted or interested.

3. Purchase Interest

According to Kotler and Keller, consumer buying interest is a consumer behavior where consumers have a desire to buy or choose a product, based on experience in choosing, using and consuming or even wanting a product. For most people, consumer behavior is often initiated and influenced by a large number of stimuli from outside themselves, both in the form of marketing stimuli and stimuli from the environment. These stimuli are then processed within oneself according to their personal characteristics, before a purchasing decision is finally made. Consumers' personal characteristics used to process these stimuli are very complex and one of them is motivation to buy.

METHODS

The type of research used in this research is quantitative research. According to Sugiono (2019:8) quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods that are based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, data collection using research instruments, quantitative or statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing hypotheses that have been established. set. This research uses a survey data collection method, namely by distributing questionnaires with data analysis techniques using multiple linear regression analysis techniques. By using a measurement scale, namely the Likert scale.

Based on the researcher's title "The influence of free shipping and advertising on buying interest from Shopee among students of the 2019 Stambuk economic education study program at HKBP Nommensen University, Pematang Siantar, the location for the researcher to carry out his research is on Jl. Sangnawaluh No.4 Pematangsiantar. This research was carried out by the researcher from October to November 2023 . The population in this study were all students from group A and B of the 2019 Stambuk Economics Education Study Program at HKBP Nommensen Pematang Siantar University, totaling 114 students. The sample in this study were all students of group B of the 2019 Stambuk Economics Education Study Program at HKBP Nommensen Pematang Siantar University, totaling 60 students.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Result

Instrument Validity and Reliability Test Results

After testing the instrument, the researcher then tabulated the results of the respondents' answers by arranging answer codes according to the classification of answers in table form. Tabulation of respondents' answers was carried out with the help of the Microsoft Excel program and using analytical data using analytical data in the SPSS 24 program . From the results of the calculations carried out you can determine whether or not the statement items in the research instrument are valid.

A statement item is declared valid if the calculated r value $>$ r table with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. From the results of the validity test , it can be seen that the correlation between each question item and the total score of $n = 31$ shows that the r table is 0.355 . Statement items that have a correlation value smaller than 0.355 are declared invalid and are not used when testing the hypothesis, while statements that have a correlation value greater than 0.355 will be used when testing the research hypothesis. Instrument reliability testing is carried out if all research instruments have been tested for validity. The instrument reliability test was carried out to determine the level of confidence in the research instrument used as a data collection tool. To calculate the reliability test of the research instrument, the Cronbach alpha formula is used. The instrument is declared reliable if the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is > 0.6 .

Instrument Validity Test

The calculation of the validity of free postage consists of 20 statement items, the advertising questionnaire consists of 20 statements, and the purchase interest questionnaire consists of 20 statements which are carried out by calculating data from the SPSS 22 program analysis. After testing and analyzing it with statistics, it is known that there are items the statement item is invalid due to r count is smaller than r table. Items that are declared valid are items that have a correlation value (r) $>$ 0.361 while items that have a correlation value (r) $>$ 0.361 are valid questionnaire items. This can be concluded that for the free postage questionnaire (X 1) it is known that in the 20-item questionnaire which has a correlation value (r) $>$ 0.361, there are 18 valid questionnaire items and there are 2 invalid questionnaires. And for the advertising questionnaire (X 2) it is known that the 20-item questionnaire has a correlation value (r) $>$ 0.361, 17 of which are valid and there are 3 invalid questionnaires. Furthermore, for the purchase interest questionnaire (Y), it is known that there are 20 items in the questionnaire that have a correlation value (r) $>$ 0.361, 17 of which are valid and there are 3 invalid questionnaires. So the questionnaire used in this research is a valid statement. Where in this research 52 questionnaire items were used in this research.

Instrument Reliability Test

For the questionnaire reliability criteria, if r count $>$ r table with a significant level ($\alpha = 0.05$) then the questionnaire is said to be reliable. However, if r count \leq r table then the questionnaire is considered to have no reliability. If the Cronbach Alpha value is $>$ 0.60 it is said to be reliable, but if the Cronbach Alpha value is $<$ 0.60 it is said to be unreliable.

Obtained r calculated = 0.742 and r table = 0.361. So r count $>$ r table and if the Cronbach Alpha value (0, 742) $>$ 0.60. From the results of free shipping reliability calculations, it can be concluded that the instruments in the research questionnaire used are reliable. Obtained r calculated = 0.804 and r table = 0.361. So r count $>$ r table and if the Cronbach Alpha value (0, 840) $>$ 0.60. From the results of advertising reliability calculations, it can be concluded that the instruments in the research questionnaire used are reliable. Obtained r calculated = 0.804 and r table = 0.361. So

rcount > rtable and if the Cronbach Alpha value (0,783) > 0.60. From the results of calculating the reliability of purchasing interest, it can be concluded that the instruments in the research questionnaire used are reliable.

Data Normality Test

Figure 1. Normal Probability P-Plot Curve

The results of the p-plot graph test show that the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the diagonal direction, which states that the data meets the assumption of normality and the data is declared to be normally distributed. This can be seen in figure 1 above.

Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	26,554	11,030		2,407	.019		
Free Shipping	,410	.127	,391	3,223	,002	,993	1,007
Advertisement	,152	.116	,159	1,312	,195	,993	1,007

a. Dependent Variable: Buying Interest

Table 1. Multicollinearity Test Results

Based on the results of these calculations, it shows that all independent variables have a value of VIF < 10 and tolerance > 0.1 . So it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables in the form of regression.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 2 Scatterplot curve

Based on Figure 2, it can be seen that the points are spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. Thus it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity does not occur.

Multiple Regression Analysis Test

The purpose of the multiple regression analysis test is to determine the direction and how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable.

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Next, the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable is tested with a confidence interval of 95% or a = 5%.

Table 2 Multiple Regression Analysis Test Results

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	26,554	11,030		2,407	.019
	Free Shipping	,410	.127	,391	3,223	,002
	Advertisem ent	,152	.116	,159	1,312	,195

a. Dependent Variable: Buying Interest

In accordance with the test results above, the following regression equation is obtained:

$$Y = a + b_1.X_1 + b_2.X_2 + e$$
$$Y = 26.554 + 0.410 X_1 + 0.152 X_2$$

Based on the regression coefficient value of the Free Shipping and Advertising variables, the influence on consumer buying interest can be explained as below, namely:

1. The constant value (a) shows a value which means that if the Free Shipping (X1) and Advertising (X2) variables have a constant value of 26.554 then the purchase interest variable is 26.554. This means that if the three independent variables decrease, purchasing decisions will also decrease.
2. The regression coefficient for Free Shipping (X1) of 0.410 shows the magnitude of the influence of Free Shipping on purchasing interest in the positive direction. This means that if the Free Shipping strategy increases by 1%, purchasing interest will increase by 0.410. If there is a decrease of 1%, the other variables' regression coefficient value, Free Shipping, will reduce Purchase Interest by 0.410.
3. The regression coefficient for advertising (X2) is 0.152, showing the magnitude of the influence of advertising on purchasing interest in the positive direction. This means that if the advertising strategy increases by 1%, purchasing interest will increase by 0.152. If there is a decrease of 1%, the other variable advertising regression coefficient value will reduce purchase interest by 0.152.
4. Equation $Y = 26.554 + 0.499 X_1 + 0.152 X_2 + e$. This concludes that the variable with the greatest value that has an influence on buying interest is Free Shipping. This is proven, among other variables, the Free Shipping regression coefficient value is the largest value.

t test

The partial test (t) is used to determine whether the hypothesis used is accepted or rejected, with a confidence level of 95% or $\alpha=5\%$, with the following conditions :

1. If $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$, then the independent variable has an effect on the dependent variable.
2. If $t \text{ count} < t \text{ table}$, then the independent variable has no effect on the dependent variable.

Table 4.3 t test results

Coefficients ^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	26,554	11,030		2,407	.019
	Free Shipping	,410	.127	,391	3,223	,002
	Advertisem ent	,152	.116	,159	1,312	,195

a. Dependent Variable: Buying Interest

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that:

1. Free shipping on purchase interest. Testing with a significance level of 0.05 and the degrees of freedom are $df = (n-k1) = (60-3-1) = 56$, the t-table is 1.6715. The statistical test that has been carried out on the Free Shipping variable on purchasing interest explains that the t-count is greater than the t-table ($3.223 > 1.6715$) and the sig. lower than 0.05 ($1,312 < 0.05$) which means the hypothesis (H1) in this study is accepted. So it can be concluded that free shipping has an effect on purchasing interest.
2. Advertising on purchase intention. Testing with a significance level of 0.05 and the degrees of freedom are $df = (n-k1) = (60-3-1) = 56$, the t-table is 1.6715. The statistical test that has been carried out on the advertising variable on purchasing interest explains that the t-count is greater than the t-table ($2.407 > 1.6715$) and the sig. greater than 0.05 ($1.312 < 0.05$) which means the hypothesis (H2) in this study is accepted. So it can be concluded that advertising influences purchasing interest.

F test

The F test is carried out to find out whether the independent variables together have an influence on the dependent variable. In this case, Fcount is compared with Ftable with the following conditions :

1. If F count > F table , then Ho is rejected and H1 is accepted
2. If F count < F table , then H1 is rejected and Ho is rejected.

Table 4 F Test Results

ANOVA ^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	969,587	2	484,794	5,738	.005 ^b
	Residual	4815.746	57	84,487		
	Total	5785.333	59			

a. Dependent Variable: y

b. Predictors: (Constant), X2, X1

Based on table 4, it is found that the Fcount value (5.734) is greater than the Ftable value (3.15). This indicates that the research results reject H0 and accept H1. Thus, simultaneously free shipping and advertising influence the buying interest variable at HKBP Nommensen University, Pematang Siantar with a significant level of influence. This gives meaning to the hypothesis which states that free shipping and consumer advertising simultaneously influence the buying interest variable at HKBP Nommensen University. Pematangsiantar is acceptable.

Coefficient of Determination Test

Table 5 Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.409 ^a	.168	.138	9.19167

a. Predictors: (Constant), Advertising, Free Shipping

Value of the coefficient of determination The Rsquare value is 0.138 or $0.138 \times 100\% = 13.8\%$, so it can be interpreted that the variables Free Shipping (X1) and Advertising (X2), simultaneously (together) have an effect on buying interest (Y) by 13.8%, then the remaining 86.2% is influenced by other variables outside the research.

Discussion

1. The Influence of Free Shipping on Interest in Purchasing Cosmetic Goods at Shopee. In accordance with the data from research that has been carried out, it can be understood that the Free Shipping variable (X1) has an influence on purchasing interest (Y). This is proven by a multiple linear regression test, Free Shipping has a regression coefficient value of 0.410. This means that if the Free Shipping strategy increases by 1%, buying interest will increase by 0.410. If there is a decrease of 1%, the other variables' regression coefficient value, Free Shipping, will reduce purchase interest by 0.410. Based on the results of the partial t-test, it is clear that $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($3.223 > 1.6715$) and the value (sig.) < 0.05 is 0.025, so it is significant. In this way, it can be said that free shipping alone (partial) has a positive effect on interest in purchasing cosmetic goods at Shopee. So the first hypothesis (H1), namely that free shipping has an effect on purchasing interest, is accepted.
2. The influence of advertising on purchase interest from Shopee is in accordance with the research data that has been carried out, so it can be understood that the advertisement variable (X2) has no influence on purchase interest (Y). This is proven by the multiple linear regression test, advertising has a regression coefficient value of 0.152. This means that if the advertising strategy increases by 1%, purchasing interest will increase by 0.152. If there is a decrease of 1%, the other variable advertising regression coefficient value will reduce purchase interest by 0.152. Based on the results of the partial t-test, it is clear that $t_{count} < t_{table}$ ($2.407 > 1.6715$) and the value (sig.) > 0.05 is 2,407, so it is significant. In

this way, it can be said that advertising alone (partially) has a positive effect on consumer purchasing interest in cosmetic goods at Shopee. So the second hypothesis (H2), namely advertising has an influence on purchase intention, is accepted.

3. The Effect of Free Shipping and Advertising on Purchase Interest from Shopee Based on the simultaneous f-test that has been carried out, it is clear that the f-count is greater than the f-table ($5.738 > 3.15$) and the significance is lower than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0, 05$). In this way, it can be interpreted that the Free Shipping and Advertising variables collectively have a significant influence on purchasing interest. The results of the research show that f-count $>$ f-table ($5,738 > 3.15$) and the significance value is <0.05 , namely 0.000. So it means that advertising and free shipping have a positive and significant influence on online buying interest.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on findings from several phases, including data collection, data processing, and data analysis regarding the influence of free shipping and shopee advertising , several conclusions were obtained, namely:

1. The results of the Free Shipping Variable Research prove that t count $>$ t table ($3.223 > 1.6715$) (sig.) $<$ 0.05 as much as 0 Free Shipping and Advertising on buying interest from Shopee 025, so it is significant. In this way, free shipping alone (partially) has a positive effect on buying interest from Shopee. So it can be concluded that free shipping has an effect on purchasing interest. I can conclude that the influence of free shipping on buying interest from Shopee is because there are many promotions for free shipping and low prices which makes consumers' buying interest increase.
2. The results of the Advertising Variable Research prove that t-count $>$ t-table ($2.407 > 1.6715$) with (sig.) $<$ 0.05, namely 0.05, so it is significant. In this way, advertising alone (partially) has a positive effect on buying interest from Shopee. So it can be concluded that advertising has an influence on purchase intention. The existence of advertisements has a big influence on buying interest from Shopee because the advertisements on Shopee are very interesting and using famous artists make students' buying interest increase.
3. Based on the results of the simultaneous t-test, it shows that the t-count is higher than the f-table ($5.738 > 3.15$) and the significance is lower than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). This can be interpreted as the Free Shipping and Advertising variables as a significant influence on buying interest. According to the research results above, free shipping and advertising have the effect of increasing buying interest. The presence of free shipping and advertising increases buying interest and encourages buyers to make purchases on Shopee.

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